

SCLEROTHERAPY: HOW TO REMOVE SPIDER VEINS EFFECTIVELY?

People especially women start avoiding short dresses or other types of leg revealing dresses because of the ugly appearance of varicose or spider veins. These ugly bunches of purple, red, or blue veins may develop on the ankles, calves, and thighs. Varicose veins are alike ailments, except that these veins point to be larger, darker, and stick out from the surface of the skin. They may not be pleasant, but they're miserably very common. In fact, it's estimated that half of all women are affected by them, along with many men. Such conditions require [spider vein treatment near me San Jose](#).

Fortunately, you can get rid of ugly veins easily with advanced technology for **vein treatments** without experiencing any pain or discomfort.

Sclerotherapy for Spider Veins: An Overview.

“Sclerotherapy” is a permanent form of **vein treatment in California** developed to treat unsightly spider and varicose veins. During treatment, the doctor injects a special chemical solution into the vein. Then, the vein drops in on itself, and the body grasps it, making it disappear. The procedure is almost painless and completes in about one hour in the doctor's office.

You may be a suitable candidate for **spider vein treatment in San Jose** if you are exhausted from your spider veins or varicose veins and are wishing for a lasting solution. Most people having good overall health can go through this treatment. This **vein treatment near me** can

be performed on adult men and women of any age, although you should not undergo sclerotherapy if you are pregnant, bedridden, or have a history of blood clotting issues. This treatment can be used on spider veins in many areas of the body.

On the day of the **vein treatment near me California**, wear loose clothing so that the doctor can access the veins. During the procedure, the doctor injects a solution. Injections are placed about every inch along the vein. Some patients encounter a lesser cramp as the solution is vaccinated, particularly if a large varicose vein is being eliminated, although most patients get the procedure to be pain-free.

Once injected, the solution makes the blood clot inside the vein, and the vein's interior walls stick together. Over time, the body will naturally occupy the vein, and within six weeks, it will disappear from view eventually. The treated veins may disappear permanently, however, the injections do not stop new spider veins from developing. There can be one to three sessions to make the targeted veins disappear effectively, although particularly large varicose veins or large clumps of spider veins may require extra sessions during [vein treatments la Jolla](#).

After a sclerotherapy treatment, there is no required downtime. Most patients can return to work just after the treatment. However, exercise and hot baths should be avoided for up to a week. There may be some swelling and bruising of the treated areas, and larger veins may become hard until they have been dissolved by the body, a process that could take several weeks. During the first few days, patients are advised by **vein specialist California** to wear support stockings, and walking is encouraged to promote healing.